

**TSG data collected during Tara Oceans expedition
2009-2012
QC validation process and SSS/SST data analysis**

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Summary report and conclusions on the whole expedition

I- Summary

The Tara Oceans expedition started in Lorient in September 2009 and ended in the same French harbour in march 2012, crossing a good part of the World Ocean : Mediterranean, Indian Ocean, North and South Atlantic and Pacific Oceans .

A thermosalinograph (TSG , Seabird SB45) and a temperature sensor (SBE38) have been recording sea surface temperature (SST) and salinity(SSS) during the whole cruise .

154 hydrographical stations have been achieved along the cruise, providing 675 CTD profiles to a maximum depth of 1000m. The CTD rosette was a Seabird 9plus system with double C and T sensors, which have been regularly factory calibrated during the expedition .CTD profiles have been processed and QC validated by the the LOV team (Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche) . Details about this validation process appear in *references [1],[2],[3]*.

Raw TSG data (recorded at 0.1 Hz) have been processed using pre and post campaign calibrations;

Those calibrated data have been then filtered and median averaged every 5 mn for the 1st year (Lorient to Cape town) and every 1mn for the rest of the cruise (Cape Town to Lorient).

They have been compared to SSS and SST averaged from surface bins of each CTD profile (when available) . For those CTD profiles who were validated as significant for intercomparison , TSG data have been corrected from the (CTD-TSG) differences.

Through this full process, Quality Controlled (QC) data for SSS and SST have been produced and are presented in this report following a geographical/chronological schedule:

Chapter 1: Data processing and analysis from Lorient to Cape Town (2009-2010). Methodology for the 5mn data processing and results.

Chapter 2: Data processing and analysis from Cape town to Lorient (2010-2012). New methodology for the 1mn data processing and results for the South Atlantic leg.

Chapter 3: Data analysis from Ushuaia to Tahiti, including Antarctica, Patagonian Channels, Galapagos leg and STEFI experiment (Marqueses Isl.)

Chapter 4: Data analysis from Tahiti to San Diego, through Hawaii

Chapter 5: Data analysis from San Diego to Savannah, through Panama Canal.

Chapter 6: Data analysis from Savannah to Lorient, through New York and Atlantic Islands

Chapter 7: Technical appendix : Seabird Calibration reports and hardware configurations for SBE45 and SBE38. Final LOV report on CTD profiles validation .

II- Comments and conclusions on global results

(CTD-TSG) differences computed leg by leg on the final QC data appear in the following table and graphs :

leg		valid CTD profiles	(CTD-TSG) SST difference [°C]		(CTD-TSG) SSS difference [PSU]	
Name	Nbr		median	std deviation	median	std deviation
Lorient to Capetown	1	89	0,0042	0,084	-0,00015	0,0185
Capetown to Ushuaia	2	82	-0,0001	0,076	0,0001	0,025
Ushuaia to Tahiti	3	114	-0,0001	0,005	-0,0008	0,01
Tahiti to San Diego	4	31	-0,0013	0,021	-0,0017	0,003
San Diego to Savannah	5	51	-0,0001	0,039	-0,0002	0,015
Savannah to Lorient	6	57	0	0,052	0	0,016

As seen on Figure 1, (CTD- TSG) median differences on final QC data are always smaller than the sensors initial accuracies (0.002°C and 0.005 PSU), except for SST difference on leg1, mostly in the central Indian Ocean. Standart deviations are greater on SST (fig 2) than on SSS (fig 3). Even if the SBE38 temperature sensor was positioned upstream from the pump as close as possible from the seawater intake ($\approx 3\text{m}$ on Tara), the SST signal was randomly biased by the ship's bilge temperature. This is obvious for the first 2 legs (stdv $\approx 0.08^\circ\text{C}$ in Indian ocean and South Atlantic), and lesser afterwards (stdv $< 0.05^\circ\text{C}$). Standart deviations on SSS (fig 3) are smaller than 0.02 PSU except for the South Atlantic leg (≈ 0.03 PSU).

Final conclusions

- From Nice to Capetown, TSG data have a low resolution (5mn) and show significant differences with CTD data, even after thorough intercalibration corrections. Most discrepancies, especially on SST, appear in the central Indian Ocean where SST was around or above 30°C and electronic problems (GPS, interface) were common.
- From Capetown to Ushuaia, resolution becomes better (1mn data until the end of expedition), median differences are smaller but their standard deviations are still high , even after numerous intercalibration corrections .
- In Antarctic Peninsula, Drake Passage and Patagonian Channels, we had no CTD profiles available for TSG intercalibration . Hence no corrections were applied and discussion is impossible.
- From Valparaiso to Tahiti, through Easter Island, Galapagos Islands and French Polynesia we had excellent statistics on TSG/CTD differences so that we did not even need to correct TSG data with intercalibration.
- From Tahiti to San Diego through Hawaii, we applied minor intercalibration corrections and we obtained small final differences with narrow standard deviations
- From San Diego to Savannah through Panama Canal, we applied some intercalibration corrections so that we obtained small final differences but with increasing standard deviations .
- From Savannah to Lorient, we applied rather strong intercalibration corrections so that we obtained differences close to zero but with broad standard deviations.

II- Deliverables

This report gives an analysis of TSG QC data for the whole Tara Oceans expedition from start to end. The QC data are delivered as ASCII files with the following format:

JJ (julian date)	Decimal JJ	date	UTC	latitude (dec. Degree)	longitude (dec. Degree)	SSS (PSU)	SST (°C ITS 90)
21797	57440	05/09/2009	15:57:20	47.30068	-3.87995	35.37406	19.48431
21797	57790	05/09/2009	16:03:10	47.29060	-3.89377	35.37647	19.45931
21797	57900	05/09/2009	16:05:00	47.28743	-3.89812	35.37907	19.46621
21797	58250	05/09/2009	16:10:50	47.27742	-3.91238	35.37997	19.44771

Data for the first year (Lorient 09/2009 to Capetown 07/2010) are 5mn median averaged in the file "taraTSGQC1.txt"

Data for the 2 following years (Capetown 09/2010 to Lorient 03/2012) are 1 mn median averaged in the file "taraTSGQC2.txt".

III- References

[Ref 1] : **Post-processing physical data acquired during the expedition TARA OCEANS (preliminary report for year 1)**, V. Taillandier, LOV, April 2011

[Ref 2] **Post-processing hydrological data acquired during the expedition TARA OCEANS, Final report**
V. Taillandier, June 2012

[Ref 3] **Process of CTD O2 and optical sensors of TARA OCEANS**
L. Berline and al., November 2012

Ref 2, which is the final report on CTD QC validated data, appears in chapter 7.

Chapter 1

Data processing and analysis from Lorient to Capetown (2009-2010)

Methodology and results

I- General

For this period we have raw TSG data sampled at 10s rate:

- start on 05/09/2009 13:59:00 in Lorient
- end on 16/07/2010 10:09:08 in Capetown

As explained in the detailed process description in appendix 1, we encountered many GPS and interface problems during this first year. Therefore we could only produce 5mn median averaged data from the raw data with numerous gaps in the time series.

II- Calibration and Quality Control (QC) processing

The process is detailed in appendix 1.

In abstract and starting from the raw 10s instrumental data:

- GPS gaps are filled when possible, otherwise *NaNs*
- SSS and SST are averaged through a running median on a 5mn window
- Remaining outliers are removed by hand (visual check on the time series) and replaced by *NaNs*.
- Calibration coefficients (from pre and post cruise factory calibrations) are applied, assuming a linear time drift.
- Using calibrated/QC CTD profiles, S and T data in a depth range from 1 to 4 m are extracted and (spatially) averaged.
- For each valid CTD profile, they are compared to simultaneous TSG data (SST and SSS averaged on a ± 10 mn window around CTD time)
- (CTD- TSG) differences on SST and SSS are plotted against time, allowing detection of trends
- If (*and only if*) these differences trends look consistent and caused by TSG, a correction is applied to TSG data (independently on SST and /or SSS), generally computed from the differences averaged leg by leg.

III- Results

III-1 Corrections from factory calibrations :

After one year, arriving in Capetown, the maximum drifts were :

- 0.00009 °C on SST
- + 0.022 PSU on SSS

Temperature drift is not significant, being less than SBE38 initial accuracy (0.002°C)

Salinity drift is significant, being 4 times the SBE45 initial accuracy (0.005 PSU).

III-2 Corrections from CTD inter comparisons :

89 CTD profiles have been considered as valid for TSG inter comparisons, among the 153 profiles validated by Vincent Taillandier [*ref 1*].

The maximum "leg" corrections (computed from the (CTD-TSG) differences averaged on the leg) are :

- + 0.55 PSU on SSS (Cyprus gyre leg)
- - 0.12°C on SST (Mumbai- Male leg)

All corrections, with corresponding valid CTD profiles are listed in appendix 2.

III-3 Final QC results :

All corrections being applied, the final TSG/QC data show the following statistics when compared to CTD/QC data through the whole domain (figure 1).

Plots of SST and SSS with CTD station positions are given in the 2 charts.

Figure 1: (CTD-TSG) differences and valid/non valid CTD profiles from Lorient to Capetown

Appendix n°1: Filtering , calibration and correction process on TSG data from Lorient to Capetown (2009-2010)

I- Filling GPS gaps on 10s raw data

During year 1, the TSG encountered major problems with GPS positions :

- Failures on the Nmea interface (the odd Seabird grey box...)
- unreliable NMEA stream issued from the ship's GPS
- overheating in the dry lab in the central Indian Ocean

Most of the gaps in the time series are due these problems . We tried to recover most of the missing data in post process by time correlations between TSG raw files and other GPS sources on board (FRRF on its own GPS, Seaclear on the board NMEA stream) . During some legs, GPS positions have therefore been interpolated:

- From Lorient (09/09) to Male (04/10) the positions have been mainly interpolated from FRRF GPS files and they are correct .The last error remaining on the Malta-Dubrovnick leg (noted by Stephane Pesant) has been successfully corrected.
- From Male to Capetown (07/10), FRRF GPS data were not reliable or unavailable , so we had to merge as well the Seaclear track files , ie the ship's NMEA stream which is not stable .

As a consequence position data in those TSG files from Male to Capetown may be randomly biased from 5 to 10mn of degree. But time remains correct and TSG time series are accurately correlated to CTD profiles time.

II- Averaging 10s raw data

A running median (window 5mn) is applied to SSS . Then the first occurrence of this median SSS value is searched in the 5 mn window ; the corresponding SST value and time stamp are associated .

This is the reason why the sampling period in the final QC data is not exactly constant and equal to 5mn .

III- Filtering outliers

Despite the median averaging, outliers still remained in the time series which were removed by various filters :

-high and low limits filter on SST /SSS:

$$13 < SST < 35 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} \quad \text{and} \quad 32 < SSS < 41 \text{ PSU}$$

-zero phase/high pass filter on SST/SSS (with window $\Delta t = 10$ mn for the running median)

$$\Delta T / \Delta t < 0.02 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} / \text{mn} \quad \Delta S / \Delta t < 0.02 \text{ PSU} / \text{mn}$$

Figure 1 : filtering outliers on SSS and SST time series (ensemble)

Figure 2 : filtering outliers on SSS and SST time series (zoom on 7 days)

Comments on noise

Typically on graph n°2 (Indian Ocean) the diurnal SST signal is physically significant, it is NOT noise (it doesn't affect SSS) and therefore must NOT be removed by the high pass filter .That's why we keep its threshold values at low level.

Noise may be induced by air bubbles in the sea water intake, especially in heavy weather and despite of the vortex debubbler. Visual detection on the time series with manual removal is the only solution.

ACS is *in line and upstream* with the TSG on the seawater duct (see chapter 7 for plumbing hardware).

Hence the ACS filtered periods (0.2 μ , 5mn every 30mn) apply as well to TSG data: in theory, they shouldn't affect T and C measurements ; but the filter's 1 liter content is released into the TSG, which means that at the start of every filtered period, "25mn old " sea water is delivered to TSG during 15s (flowrate 4lt/mn). This periodic noise doesn't show up in the 5mn median averaged data, but it is obvious in the 10s raw data .

IV- TSG Calibration

T1 and C sensors on SBE45 and T2 sensor on SBE38 have been factory calibrated:

- On purchase on 13/may/2009
- On arrival at Capetown on 04/aug/2010

Calibration reports and applied algorithm are detailed in chapter 7.

Principle :

- Raw 10s files with T1/C/T2 are no more available due to interface problems on board during 1st year, we only have access to 5mn averaged SST (T2 from SBE38) and SSS (computed from T1 and C)
- By linear interpolation between calibration dates, we compute C slope and offset on T for the julian date of each data .
- We apply the offset to each SST data
- We apply the C slope to each SSS data

Correction values function of time appear on graph n° 3

Figure 4 : calibration corrections on SST and SSS during the whole campaign

After one year, arriving in Capetown , the maximum drifts were :

- 0.00009 °C on SST

+ 0.022 PSU on SSS

Temperature drift is not significant , being less than SBE38 initial accuracy (0.002°C)

Salinity drift is significant, being 4 times the SBE45 initial accuracy (0.005 PSU) .

We estimate (by simulation on raw files) that *correcting salinity instead of conductivity* induces an error less than 0.005PSU.

IV- Cross comparison with CTD profiles

IV-1 Principle

V. Taillandier has processed the 153 CTD downcast profiles, binaveraged to 1m for the Nice - Capetown legs. Data are calibrated and quality controlled using crosscomparison from the double T and C sensors, but no salinity bottles have been sampled during this period [ref 1]

In each CTD profile :

- We extract T/S data for depth range 1-4m (when available... not always) with their julian date
- We compute spatial averages and stdv.
- For each CTD profile, they are compared to simultaneous TSG data (SST and SSS averaged on a ± 10 mn window around CTD time, graph 4)
- (CTD- TSG)differences on SST and SSS are plotted against time, allowing detection of difference trends (graph 5)

Figure 4 : CTD & TSG SST/SSS on the whole period

Figure 5 : (CTD-TSG) SST and SSS differences

Comments :

- With a ± 10 mn time window on TSG and a depth range of 1-4m on CTD, we find 96 comparison points among the 153 CTD profiles.
- Difference values are very heterogeneous over the period and may reach 1.5°C and 1 PSU!
- Therefore each individual CTD profile must be carefully studied in order to validate or unvalidate it for TSG corrections.

IV-2 Example on the Cyprus Gyre Leg.

Figure 6 shows the CTD profiles (n°28 to 39), with a well developed mixing layer down to 50m. Zooming into the first 10 meters shows that all profiles give significant data in the 1-4m range. *A priori* we consider all these profiles as valid for CTD/TSG comparison.

Figure 7 shows the comparison and the calculated differences.

All CTD salinities show an average offset of 0.55 PSU with the TSG , except cast n° 29 (0.95 PSU).

All CTD temperature show an average offset less than 0.1°C except casts n° 30, 34 and 29.

These 3 CTD casts are simultaneous with noisy parts on the TSG time series (turbulence?).

We compute the averaged differences on the leg, *discarding these 3 casts* .

Average SST difference = +0.009°C Average SSS difference = +0.548 PSU .

We apply these corrections to the TSG data and obtain the corrected time plots on graph n°8.

IV-3 Corrections for all other legs

A similar processing has been applied to all legs from Nice to Capetown . Corrections values are summarized in appendix 2.

Valid CTD profiles for TSG corrections have dropped to 89.

Some legs show no corrections on TSG, because no CTD profiles were available :

- From Lorient to Nice , we had no rosette with SBE911 on board but only a small SBE19 standalone , whose data have not been post-processed at LOV .
- From Nice to Malta , the TSG had such random failures that all CTD profiles occurred unluckily during TSG gaps.

Some legs were split into several sessions with various corrections values, due to notably different error patterns (fouling in the TSG sea water intake ?).

Figure 6: CTD stations on Cyprus Gyre Leg

Figure 7: Cyprus Gyre, calibrated SST and SSS before TSG corrections, TSG / CTD time series and differences

Figure 8: Cyprus Gyre, calibrated SST and SSS after TSG corrections, TSG / CTD time series

Figure 9: Cyprus Gyre QC data

Appendix n°2 : CTD stations log sheet with related corrections on TSG data

ODV #stn	Leg	Station	Pressure (dbar)	CTD Post Proc comments	CTD valid for TSG (Y/N)	corr SST (*C)	corr SSS (PSU)	TSG comments
	Lorient-Nice			SBE19 data not processed	N	0,000	0,000	no CTd
	Nice	1		stopped at datcnv				
1	Nice	2	908	S spikes at thermocline (50m)	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
2	Nice - Bizerte	12	1678	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
3	Nice - Bizerte	12	275	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
4	Nice - Bizerte	12	510	bad values in surface bins	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
5	Bizerte - Naples	14	805	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
6	Naples - Malta	16	210	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
7	Naples - Malta	16	840	TC1 unstable at 220m, TC2 at 360m	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
8	Naples - Malta	16	410	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
9	Naples - Malta	17	205	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
10	Naples - Malta	17	265	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
11	Malta - Malta	18	225	RAS	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
12	Malta - Malta	18	740	S spikes at thermocline (60m)	N	0,000	0,000	no valid CTd
13	Malta - Dubrovnik	21	900	S spikes at thermocline (60m)	N	0,003	0,392	
14	Malta - Dubrovnik	21	430	S spikes at thermocline (60m)	Y	0,003	0,392	
15	Malta - Dubrovnik	22	210	RAS	Y	0,003	0,392	
16	Malta - Dubrovnik	22	740	layered in 0-100m	Y	0,003	0,392	
17	Malta - Dubrovnik	22	205	RAS	N	0,003	0,392	
18	Malta - Dubrovnik	23	203	low S in 0-20m	N	0,003	0,392	
19	Malta - Dubrovnik	23	460	RAS	Y	0,003	0,392	
20	Malta - Dubrovnik	23	203	TC1 unstable at 160m	Y	0,003	0,392	
21	Dubrovnik - Dubrovnik	24	285	RAS	N			no TSG
22	Dubrovnik - Dubrovnik	24	255	RAS	N			no TSG
23	Dubrovnik - Athens	25	212	RAS	Y	-0,065	0,455	TSG unreliable
24	Dubrovnik - Athens	25	970	RAS	N	-0,065	0,455	TSG unreliable
25	Dubrovnik - Athens	25	206	RAS	N	-0,065	0,455	TSG unreliable
26	Dubrovnik - Athens	26	205	S spikes at thermocline (50m)	N	-0,065	0,455	TSG unreliable
27	Dubrovnik - Athens	26	480	S spikes at thermocline (50m)	N	-0,065	0,455	TSG unreliable
28	Athens - Beyruth	27	882	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
29	Athens - Beyruth	27	950	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	N	0,009	0,548	
30	Athens - Beyruth	27	632	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	N	0,009	0,548	
	Athens - Beyruth	27	330	pressure data corrupted	N	0,009	0,548	
31	Athens - Beyruth	27	967	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
32	Athens - Beyruth	27	993	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
33	Athens - Beyruth	27	992	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
34	Athens - Beyruth	28	987	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	N	0,009	0,548	
35	Athens - Beyruth	28	1006	bad values in surface bins	Y	0,009	0,548	
36	Athens - Beyruth	28	981	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
37	Athens - Beyruth	28	999	S more spiky	Y	0,009	0,548	
38	Athens - Beyruth	28	1004	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,009	0,548	
39	Cyprus - Beyruth	28	1004	S more spiky	Y	0,009	0,548	
40	Cyprus - Beyruth	28	1004	S more spiky	N	0,023	0,053	
41	Beyruth - Alexandrie	29	972	S spikes at thermocline (140m)	Y	-0,035	0,017	

42	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	196	RAS	Y	-0,035	0,017	
43	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	992	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	-0,035	0,017	
44	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	135	RAS	Y	-0,035	0,017	
45	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	126	RAS	N	-0,035	0,017	
46	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	120	RAS	Y	-0,035	0,017	
47	Beyruth Alexandrie	-	30	426	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	-0,035	0,017	
48	Sharm - Jeddah1	31	298	RAS	Y	0,011	0,040		
49	Sharm - Jeddah1	31	886	RAS	N	0,011	0,040		
50	Sharm - Jeddah1	32	219	RAS	Y	0,011	0,040		
51	Sharm - Jeddah1	32	952	RAS	Y	0,011	0,040		
52	Sharm - Jeddah1	32	208	RAS	Y	0,011	0,040		
53	Sharm - Jeddah1	33	155	RAS	N	0,011	0,040		
54	Sharm - Jeddah1	33	640	RAS	N	0,011	0,012		
55	Sharm - Jeddah2	34	203	RAS	Y	0,002	0,012		
56	Sharm - Jeddah2	34	982	RAS	Y	0,002	0,012		
	Sharm - Jeddah	34		pressure data corrupted	N	0,000	0,012		
57	AbuDhabi-Masqat	36	309	RAS	Y	-0,118	0,012		
58	AbuDhabi-Masqat	36	866	layered until 400m	Y	-0,118	0,012		
59	AbuDhabi-Masqat	36	932	layered until 400m	Y	-0,118	0,012		
60	Masqat-Mumbai1	36	1011	TC1 bad profile	N	-0,019	0,180		
61	Masqat-Mumbai1	36	300	RAS	N	-0,019	0,180		
62	Masqat-Mumbai1	36	668	diff characteristics in deep layer (60-62)	Y	-0,019	0,180		
	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	213	bad profile		-0,019	0,180		
63	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	702	surface layer missing (0-50m)	Y	-0,019	0,180		
64	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	741	TC1 bad profile	N	-0,019	0,180		
65	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	739	RAS	Y	-0,019	0,180		
66	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	736	C1 lost 0.05 PSU in 200-600m	Y	-0,019	0,180		
67	Masqat-Mumbai1	37	1512	RAS	Y	-0,019	0,180		
68	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	1011	layered in 0-100m	Y	-0,082	0,030		
69	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	296	layered in 0-100m	N	-0,082	0,030		
70	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	295	TC1 and TC2 unstable in 0-50m	N	-0,082	0,030		
71	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	1003	layered in 0-100m	Y	-0,082	0,030		
72	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	489	layered in 0-100m	N	-0,082	0,030		
73	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	481	layered in 0-100m	N	-0,082	0,030		
	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	500	stopped at datcnv	N	-0,082	0,030		
74	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	475	layered in 0-100m	Y	-0,082	0,030		
75	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	474	layered in 0-100m	Y	-0,082	0,030		
76	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	479	RAS	N	-0,082	0,030		
77	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	485	RAS	N	-0,082	0,030		
78	Masqat-Mumbai2	38	1489	RAS	Y	-0,082	0,030		
79	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	997	short layers in thermocline (front?)	Y	-0,082	0,030		
80	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	485	RAS	N	-0,082	0,030		
81	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	1476	RAS	N	-0,082	0,012		
82	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	1000	layered in 0-200m	Y	-0,082	0,012		
83	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	502	layered in 0-200m	N	-0,082	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs	
84	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	493	layered in 0-200m	N	-0,082	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs	
85	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	489	smoother than previous profiles	N	-0,082	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs	
86	Masqat-Mumbai2	39	487	slight differences between C1 and C2	N	-0,082	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs	

	Masqat-Mumbai3	39	1000	pressure data corrupted	N	-0,093	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs
	Masqat-Mumbai3	39	500	pressure data corrupted	N	-0,093	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs
87	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	1445	layered until 400m	N	-0,093	0,012	TSG spikes during CTDs
88	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	486	layered until 400m	Y	-0,093	0,012	
89	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	497	layered until 400m	Y	-0,093	0,012	
90	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	498	layered until 400m	Y	-0,093	0,012	
91	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	497	layered until 400m	Y	-0,093	0,012	
92	Masqat-Mumbai3	40	494	smoother profiles than previous	N	-0,093	0,012	
93	Mumbai-Male	41	973	RAS	N	-0,120	0,109	
94	Mumbai-Male	41	489	RAS	N	-0,120	0,109	
95	Mumbai-Male	41	492	RAS	N	-0,120	0,109	
96	Mumbai-Male	41	1495	RAS	N	-0,120	0,109	
97	Mumbai-Male	42	1007	S spikes at thermocline (100m)	Y	-0,120	0,109	
98	Mumbai-Male	42	503	S spikes at thermocline (100m)	Y	-0,120	0,109	
99	Mumbai-Male	42	1512	S spikes at thermocline (100m)	Y	-0,120	0,109	
100	Mumbai-Male	43	51	RAS	Y	-0,120	0,109	
101	Male-StBrandon	44	1003	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,022	0,013	
102	Male-StBrandon	44	505	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,022	0,013	
	Male-StBrandon	44	14	only soak	N	0,022		
103	Male-StBrandon	44	270	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,022	0,013	
104	Male-StBrandon	44	270	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	0,022	0,013	
105	Male-StBrandon	44	980	C1 unstable under 800m	Y	0,022	0,013	
106	Male-StBrandon	45	506	layered until 150m	Y	0,022	0,013	
107	Male-StBrandon	45	504	layered until 150m	N	0,022	0,013	
108	Male-StBrandon	45	503	layered until 150m	N	0,022	0,013	
109	Male-StBrandon	45	500	smoother profiles than previous	N	0,022	0,013	
110	Male-StBrandon	45	495	smoother profiles than previous	N	0,022	0,013	
111	Male-StBrandon	45	890	RAS	N	0,022	0,013	
112	Male-StBrandon	46	65,5	RAS	N	0,022	0,013	
113	Male-StBrandon	47	955	RAS	N	0,022	0,013	
114	Male-StBrandon	48	877	RAS	Y	0,022	0,013	
115	Male-StBrandon	48	485	RAS	N	0,022	0,013	
116	Male-StBrandon	48	482	RAS	N	0,022	0,013	
	Male-StBrandon	49	9	only soak				
117	Mauritius-Reunion	50	1404	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
118	Mauritius-Reunion	50	982	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
119	Mauritius-Reunion	50	533	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
120	Mauritius-Reunion	50	194	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
121	Mauritius-Reunion	50	205	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
122	Mauritius-Reunion	51	1360	RAS	N	0,004	0,005	
123	Mauritius-Reunion	51	1050	RAS	N	0,004	0,005	
124	Mauritius-Reunion	51	240	RAS	Y	0,004	0,005	
125	Reunion-Madagascar	52	1474	RAS	Y	0,005	0,009	
126	Reunion-Madagascar	52	231	RAS	Y	0,005	0,009	
127	Reunion-Madagascar	52	489	RAS	N	0,005	0,009	
128	Madagascar-Mayotte	53	1515	RAS	Y	0,005	0,009	
129	Madagascar-Mayotte	53	994	RAS	Y	0,005	0,009	
	Madagascar-Mayotte	54	25	profile 0-25m without soak	N			
	Madagascar-	54	25	profile 0-25m without soak	N			

	Mayotte							
130	Mayotte-CapeTown1	55	1143	S spikes at thermocline (60m)	Y	-0,010	0,003	
131	Mayotte-CapeTown1	56	1262	S spikes at thermocline (90m)	N	-0,010	0,003	
132	Mayotte-CapeTown1	57	1009	S spikes at thermocline (90m)	Y	-0,010	0,003	
133	Mayotte-CapeTown1	58	1482	bad values of C1 in surface bins	Y	-0,010	0,003	
134	Mayotte-CapeTown1	58	1254	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
135	Mayotte-CapeTown1	58	367	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
136	Mayotte-CapeTown1	58	1018	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
137	Mayotte-CapeTown1	59	957	S spikes at thermocline (60m)	Y	-0,010	0,003	
138	Mayotte-CapeTown1	60	924	S spikes at thermocline (80m)	Y	-0,010	0,003	
139	Mayotte-CapeTown1	61	942	spike at 600m on both TC	Y	-0,010	0,003	
140	Mayotte-CapeTown1	63	867	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
141	Mayotte-CapeTown1	64	1533	RAS	N	-0,010	0,003	
142	Mayotte-CapeTown1	64	319?	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
143	Mayotte-CapeTown1	64	1193	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
144	Mayotte-CapeTown1	64	1213	RAS	Y	-0,010	0,003	
145	Mayotte-CapeTown2	64	1006	RAS	N	-0,007	0,003	
146	Mayotte-CapeTown2	64	489	layered at 175m	N	-0,007	0,003	
147	Mayotte-CapeTown2	65	1241	layered between 100-150m	N	-0,007	0,003	
148	Mayotte-CapeTown2	65	68	RAS	Y	-0,007	0,003	
149	Mayotte-CapeTown2	65	68	RAS	Y	-0,007	0,003	
150	Mayotte-CapeTown2	65	1138	RAS	Y	-0,007	0,003	
151	Mayotte-CapeTown2	65	1073	RAS	N	-0,007	0,003	
152	Mayotte-CapeTown3	66	456	RAS	Y	0,009	0,016	
	Mayotte-CapeTown3	66	68	bad profile, in stairs	N	0,009	0,016	
	Mayotte-CapeTown3	66	70	bad profile, in stairs	N	0,009	0,016	
153	Mayotte-CapeTown3	66	1259	RAS	Y	0,009	0,016	

Chapter 2

Data processing and analysis from Capetown to Lorient (2010-2012)

Methodology and results for the South Atlantic basin

I- TSG raw data processing

I-1 Subsampling 10s raw data

For the period Capetown (09/2010) to arrival in Lorient (03/2012) we have TSG raw data at 10s sampling rate with reliable GPS positions, which we process as following:

- splitting the whole (enormous!) data set in smaller files corresponding to ocean basins which are delimited on figure 1 : South Atlantic, South Pacific, North Pacific, East Pacific , North Atlantic
- sub sampling SST (from SBE 38 sensor) at 1mn , using a running median on a 1mn window
- extracting T , C, S data (from TSG SBE45) corresponding to the 1rst occurrence of the median SST inside each 1mn window

This is the reason why sampling period in the final QC data is not exactly constant and equal to 1 mn.

I-2 Raw data calibration

T1 and C sensors on SBE45 and T2 sensor on SBE38 have been factory calibrated :

- During stopover at Capetown (04/08/2010)
- After arrival at Lorient (13/06/2012)
- *We assume that sensors have been drifting linearly between calibrations* and we apply the linear interpolation process (as explained in chapter 7) to compute C slope and offsets on T1 and T2 for the julian date of each data.
- We apply the T offset to each T1 and T2 data
- We apply the slope to C
- Using Unesco equation , we compute a calibrated salinity SSScal (T1cal,Ccal)

Calibration corrections appear in figure 2 for the period Capetown (07/09/2010)-Ushuaia (19/12/2010).

Figure 2: Calibration corrections from Capetown to Ushuaia

I- 3 Raw data filtering

If we now compare the 1mn time series for

- Raw salinity processed in real time by SBE 45 (hence non calibrated)
- Calibrated salinity SSScal computed in post proc from calibrated C and T1
- « cow boy salinity » computed by applying C slope to raw SBE45 salinity (which was the process used for the 5 mn data from year 1 , leg Lorient to Capetown)

We can see on figure 3 that:

- « cow boy salinity » is in average 0.005 PSU higher than the true calibrated salinity , inducing lower precision for year 1 QC data compared to year 2 and 3 data.
- A 25 mn periodic noise on the salinities, which is due to the 0.2 μ filter from ACS positioned upstream on the seawater circuit feeding SBE45 and activated every 25mn during 5mn through an automatic 3 ways valve .
- This periodic noise is visible on C and T1 from SBE45 but not on T2 from SBE38 , which is positioned close to the sea cock and upstream from the ACS filter (see plumbing hardware in chapter 7).
- This is the reason why we decided to start the process with sub sampling the raw T2 from SBE38 (by running median), and afterwards choose the corresponding C and T1 in the 1mn window

Figure 3: SBE45 1 mn median subsampled salinities

The whole filtering process includes

- suppressing outliers with min/max and lowpass filters
- filtering the 25 mn periodic noise with a running median on a ± 6 mn window centred on the data

Filtered data are shown in figure 4, where the periodic noise has disappeared.

Figure 4 : 6mn median filtered SST and SSS

II- CTD data assimilation and inter calibration process

LOV /Villefranche has processed the 675 CTD downcast profiles, binaveraged to 1m for the 2.5 years campaign. Data are calibrated and quality controlled ,using cross-comparison between the double sensors (C,T) on the rosette , but no salinity bottles have been sampled during this period [ref 1]

In each CTD profile for the South Atlantic period (see station list in appendix 1) :

- We extract T/S data for depth range 2-4m (when available... not always) with their julian date
- they are compared to simultaneous TSG data (SST and SSS median averaged on a ± 10 mn window around CTD time (figure 5a)
- (CTD- TSG) differences on SST and SSS are plotted against time (figure 5b) and on distribution histograms (figure 5c)

Those difference graphs allow to:

- identify atypical CTD profiles , which will be discarded for the further intercalibration process (red dots on figure 5b : 12 profiles discarded among 94 available)
- identify difference trends : stations 68-69-70 show an average bias of 0.6 PSU on SSS, possibly caused by TSG duct obstruction (zoom on figure 5d)

We compute median averaged differences on SST and SSS for those 3 stations and we correct the corresponding TSG time serie.

Corrected SSS and SST appears on figure 6a, where SSS offset has disappeared.

We go on screening the whole data set , looking for other (smaller) bias and, if justified, we apply local median corrections for each station or group of stations.

(CTD-TSG) differences on the final QC data appear on figures 6b and 6c: distributions are more symmetrical than before intercalibration corrections. They are centred on small median differences (0. 12 mC and 0.13mPSU) , which are 10 times smaller than the sensors initial accuracy.

Figure 5a : SST and SSS compared from TSG series and 3-4 dbars data on CTD profiles

Figure 5b: (CTD-TSG) differences on SST and SSS

Figure 5c : (CTD-TSG) SST and SSS differences histograms before intercalibration

Figure 5d : zoom on obvious CTD/TSG difference on SSS during stations 68 to70 (Sept 18-19)

Figure 6a : zoom on the SSS/SST after intercalibration for stations 68 -70

Figure 6b : (CTD-TSG) differences time series after intercalibration corrections for the whole stations

Figure 6b : (CTD-TSG) differences distributions after intercalibration corrections for the whole stations

III- Detailed data analysis for each leg in the South Atlantic basin

Having obtained QC validated time series for the whole South Atlantic basin, we can now analyse each specific leg with more details .

III-1 From Capetown to Rio de Janeiro (figure 7)

Long gaps are visible in the TSG data , due to repetitive failures on the instrument . Though the cold and fresh Bengala current appears clearly on the south eastern side of the basin .

III-2 From Rio de Janeiro to Buenos Aires (figure 8)

Fresh and cold water is visible at the entrance of Rio de la Plata

III-2 From Buenos Aires to Ushuaia (figure 8)

Malvinas Current influence is visible on the continental shelf along the eastern Argentinean shores.
Fresh water appears at start (outlet of Rio de la Plata) and arrival (entering Beagle Channel).

Figure 7 : TSG QC data and CTD stations from Capetown to Rio

Figure 8 : TSG QC data and CTD stations from Rio to Buenos Aires

Figure 9 : TSG QC data and CTD stations from Buenos Aires to Ushuaia

Appendix 1 : CTD Station list from CT to Ushuaia

date	station number	max depth	CTD profile File name	Comments			valid for Tsg corr
01/09/2010	FBT	60	tara_sbe_9C_100901_01	TEST in False Bay	SAL NOK	OK	-1
				Benguela Station			
06/09/2010	67	100	tara_sbe_9C_100906_01	CTD only			1
07/09/2010	67	100	tara_sbe_9C_100907_01	Long station - very productive water			1
07/09/2010	67	125	tara_sbe_9C_100907_02	Long station			1
07/09/2010	67	130	tara_sbe_9C_100907_03	Long station			1
07/09/2010	67	150	tara_sbe_9C_100907_04	Long station			1
08/09/2010	67	140	tara_sbe_9C_100908_01	CTD only			1
08/09/2010	67	150	tara_sbe_9C_100908_02	CTD only			1
08/09/2010	67	280	tara_sbe_9C_100908_03	CTD only			1
08/09/2010	67	400	tara_sbe_9C_100908_04	CTD only			1
				Eddy Station			
12/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100912_01	CTD only			1
12/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100912_02	CTD only - Counter in error, CTD into Block (!)			-1
12/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100912_03	CTD only - UVP did not start. RUN FLASH INITIALIZE			1
12/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100912_04	CTD only. No UVP. Counter fixed (onto spindle)			1
12/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100912_05	CTD only. UVP relay replaced.			1
13/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100913_01	CTD only			1
13/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100913_02	CTD only			1
13/09/2010	68	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100913_03	CTD only. Pb with UVP analog ONLY			1
13/09/2010	68	900	tara_sbe_9C_100913_04	CTD only (Celine).Pb with UVP analog			1
13/09/2010	68	740	tara_sbe_9C_100913_05	MESO-CTD. ISUS not connected, UVP analog not connected	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
13/09/2010	68	740	tara_sbe_9C_100913_06	MESO-CTD. ISUS not connected, UVP analog not connected	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
13/09/2010	68	740	tara_sbe_9C_100913_07	MESO-CTD. UVP set to picture			1
13/09/2010	68	740	tara_sbe_9C_100913_08	MESO-CTD. UVP reset to vignettes			1
13/09/2010	68	190	tara_sbe_9C_100913_09	LONG STATION: Shallow CTD			1
14/09/2010	68	1550	tara_sbe_9C_100914_01	LONG STATION: Deep CTD.No ISUS	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
				Short Station			
17/09/2010	69	800	tara_sbe_9C_100917_01				1
18/09/2010	69	450	tara_sbe_9C_100918_01				1
21/09/2010	70	850	tara_sbe_9C_100921_01	Long Station			1
21/09/2010	70	220	tara_sbe_9C_100921_02				1
22/09/2010	70	850	X	MESO - 1 Data lost had to FLASH INTT after MESO#4			
22/09/2010	70	850	tara_sbe_9C_100922_02	MESO - 2 No ISUS	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
22/09/2010	70	850	tara_sbe_9C_100922_03	MESO - 3			1
22/09/2010	70	850	tara_sbe_9C_100922_04	MESO - 4 only to 884m, RUN FLASH INITIALIZE	O2 NOK	O2NOK	1
22/09/2010	70	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100922_05	CTD only			1
22/09/2010	70	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100922_06	CTD only			1
				Short Station			
28/09/2010	71	850	tara_sbe_9C_100928_01	4 Deepest bottles not closed. Did not reach Activation			1
28/09/2010	71	1000	tara_sbe_9C_100928_02	Changed Bottle Closure Logic, deepest Bottle 920m. New UVP shunt			1
				Ascension Island			
04/10/2010	72	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101004_01	ISUS stopped started at depth, unknown reason. 2x files merged	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
05/10/2010	72	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101005_01				1
05/10/2010	72	250	tara_sbe_9C_101005_02				1
06/10/2010	72	850	tara_sbe_9C_101006_01	meso #1 - processed data starts at 13m. Hex file edited minus 2 lines OK			-1
06/10/2010	72	850	tara_sbe_9C_101006_02	meso #2			1

06/10/2010	72	850	tara_sbe_9C_101006_03	meso #3			1
06/10/2010	72	850	tara_sbe_9C_101006_04	meso #4			1
				Short Station			
09/10/2010	73	1550	tara_sbe_9C_101009_01	No ISUS	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
09/10/2010	73	300	tara_sbe_9C_101009_02	ISUS stopped started again at depth. 2x files merged	ISUS NOK	ISUS NOK	1
				Short Station			
12/10/2010	74	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101012_01				1
12/10/2010	74	300	tara_sbe_9C_101012_02	Thar she blows. RUN FLASH INITIALIZE. Lost last 5m only			1
				Short Station			
14/10/2010	75	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101014_01	Barracuda!			1
14/10/2010	75	400	tara_sbe_9C_101014_02	Wetlabs Deck Darks after cast			1
				Long Station			
16/10/2010	76	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101016_01				1
16/10/2010	76	300	tara_sbe_9C_101016_02				1
16/10/2010	76	200	tara_sbe_9C_101016_03	For DCM water			1
16/10/2010	76	200	tara_sbe_9C_101016_04	For DCM water			1
16/10/2010	76	200	tara_sbe_9C_101016_05	For DCM water			1
17/10/2010	76	800	tara_sbe_9C_101017_01	MESO #1 ISUS 2x files merged			1
17/10/2010	76	800	tara_sbe_9C_101017_02	MESO #2			1
17/10/2010	76	800	tara_sbe_9C_101017_03	MESO #3			1
17/10/2010	76	800	tara_sbe_9C_101017_04	MESO #4			1
				RIO DE JANEIRO			
01/11/2010	77	850	tara_sbe_9C_101101_01	Short Station - Btl 6 not closed			1
01/11/2010	77	400	tara_sbe_9C_101101_02				1
				Long Station			
03/11/2010	78	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101103_01	CTD transect - SBE 17 disarmed	ISUS NOK		-1
03/11/2010	78	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101103_02	CTD transect - Disarmed - Memory full: data to 447m on upcast			-1
04/11/2010	78	1000	X	CTD transect - Memory full not seen... no data			-1
04/11/2010	78	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101104_02	RUN FLASH INITIALIZE.			1
04/11/2010	78	400	tara_sbe_9C_101104_03				1
04/11/2010	78	160	tara_sbe_9C_101104_04	DCM bottles instead of deep pumping			1
04/11/2010	78	160	tara_sbe_9C_101104_05	DCM bottles instead of deep pumping	SAL NOK	SAL NOK	-1
04/11/2010	78	160	tara_sbe_9C_101104_06	DCM bottles instead of deep pumping			1
05/11/2010	78	860	X	No bottle closed, depth not reached due to drift (F data only)			
05/11/2010	78	860	tara_sbe_9C_101105_02	MESO #2			1
05/11/2010	78	860	X	MESO #3: Bottles closed but no Data! (F data only)			
05/11/2010	78	860	X	MESO #4: Bottles closed but no Data! (F data only)			
05/11/2010	78	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101105_05	CTD transect - UVP data loss from surface to 15m	BB NOK	BB NOK	1
06/11/2010	78	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101106_01	CTD transect - SBE17 disarmed			1
				Short Station			
08/11/2010	79	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101108_01	1000m bottles not closed			1
08/11/2010	79	1050	X	NO DATA besides UVP? No bottle			
08/11/2010	79	440	tara_sbe_9C_101108_03				1
				BUENOS AIRES			
				Custom seabird processing. Very strange: phantom 17m start to surf (manual edit hex)			
26/11/2010	79b	25	tara_sbe_9C_101126_01				-1

29/11/2010	80	840	tara_sbe_9C_101129_01	Didn't reach activation			1
29/11/2010	80	840	tara_sbe_9C_101129_02				1
29/11/2010	80	130	tara_sbe_9C_101129_03	DCM water #1	SAL NOK		-1
29/11/2010	80	130	tara_sbe_9C_101129_04	DCM water #2			1
29/11/2010	80	130	tara_sbe_9C_101129_05	DCM water #3			1
02/12/2010	81	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101202_01	Salinities			-1
02/12/2010	81	300	tara_sbe_9C_101202_02				1
06/12/2010	82	1000	tara_sbe_9C_101206_01	Winch read-out failed, depth by time			1
06/12/2010	82	400	tara_sbe_9C_101206_02	depth by time			1
07/12/2010	82	500	tara_sbe_9C_101207_01				1
				Temperature sensor replaced			
16/12/2010	83	100	tara_sbe_9C_101216_01	Bottom depth 100m. At Lemaire Strait			-1
17/12/2010	83	200	tara_sbe_9C_101217_01	Other side of Lemaire Strait...			-1

Chapter 3

Data processing and analysis from Ushuaia to Tahiti

I- TSG raw data extraction , calibration and filtering

Start: Ushuaia (Argentina) on 31/12/2010 22:50:29 (New year at sea !!!)

End: Papeete (Tahiti) on 16/08/2011 16:11:27

Calibrating T(SBE38) and S(SBE45) through T and C(SBE45) from pre- an post-campaign Seabird calibrations gives the following corrections for the period :

T correction is 10 times smaller than the SBE38 initial accuracy.(0.002°C)

S correction is of the same order of the SBE45 initial accuracy. (0.005 PSU)

The raw data were rather clean in the pacific basin , where very few data were removed by prefiltering .In the Patagonian channels , fresh water noisy sections were removed (for $S < 10$ PSU). The ACS 25mn noise was removed by the ± 6 mn window running median filter.

II- CTD profiles assimilation

CTD stations	number	% total
total	196	100%
discarded	12	6%
no 3-4db data	70	36%
valid for TSG_QC	114	58%

Among the 196 available profiles from LOV(see listing at the end) , 114 were useful for TSG intercalibration; 70 profiles showed no surface data .

12 profiles were discarded due to random and non significant (CTD-TSG) differences (red dots on figure 2): From Galapagos to Marqueses only 1 profile had to be discarded.

We have unfortunately NO valid CTD in Antarctica (between Ushuaia and Puerto Williams) mainly because we had to use there the standalone CTD and achieved very few profile , due to the hydraulic winch failure .

Screening the whole set of valid CTD data , *we decided to apply NO corrections on TSG* as the difference distributions on each station or group of stations always showed symmetrical behaviour with small median differences . This point is further detailed in the analysis of the equatorial transect and the STEFI experiment .

The difference distributions on the whole set of QC validated data appear on figure 3 :

Median differences are smaller than the instrumental accuracies and the distributions are almost Gaussian like .

This long set of data (population of 114 profiles) looks remarkably robust .

Figure 2 : (CTD-TSG) differences and valid/ non valid CTD stations

Figure 3 : (CTD-TSG) differences distribution on the final QC validated data

III- Data analysis for the Antarctic leg (Ushuaia to Puerto Williams, figure 4)

Due to large gaps in the TSG data and low number of CTD casts during this leg , no CTD profiles is ever synchronous from TSG data . Though those CTD close to TSG data look in good accordance in the time series. Fresher water is visible at the outlet of Beagle Channel (at start and end of leg) and close to the ice edge in the Weddell sea (surface melt water at station 86) .

The signature of the Antarctic convergence can be seen on the SST profile during the southerly bound crossing of Drake Passage .

IV- Data analysis from Puerto Williams to Valparaiso (figure 5)

The only 2 valid CTD profiles were obtained in the open ocean reaching Valparaiso at the very end of the leg . Hence TSG data inside the Patagonian channels from PuertoWilliams to Isla Chiloe cannot be fully trusted. Fresh water input in front of river mouth or glacier fronts were of course expected as seen on the charts.

V- Data analysis from Valparaiso to Easter Island (figure 6)

Nice continuous SST/SSS section (almost no gaps) . with most CTD profiles validated . The cold fresh waters produced by the Chilean upwelling are obvious on the charts .

Figure 4 : TSG QC data from Ushuaia to Puerto Willia

Figure 5 : TSG QC data from Puerto Williams to Valparaiso

Figure 6 : TSG QC data from Valparaiso to Easter Island

VI- Data analysis from Easter Island to Gambiers Archipelago (figures 7 & 8)

The long pacific transect from Easter Island to Quayaquil (Equator) has been sampled twice, first in April and then 1.5 month later , with rather similar tracks onwards and backwards (fig 7a and 7b). In spite of this time/space variability the same general patterns are found in the corresponding SSS/SST series.

Between Galapagos and Guayaquil , an equatorial transect was sampled by crossing the equator at 84.5W on a NS course (fig 8a and 8b).The whole transect from station 103 to 110 was spread on 20days , hence there may be a slight time/weather induced variability in the data .

Cross comparison with surface data from 20 valid CTD profiles (fig 8a low) shows a quiet good correlation , *with median differences around 0.002 °C and 0.0015 PSU*. *It must be emphasized that TSG and CTD data are true independent variables in this case* (TSG data have NOT been cross-corrected from CTD data in the whole pacific leg).

Figure 7a : TSG QC data from Easter Island to Gambiers Islands

Figure 7b : TSG QC data from Easter Island to Gambiers Islands

Figure 8a : TSG QC data for the equatorial transect , near Galapagos Isl

Figure 8b : TSG QC data for the equatorial transect , near Galapagos

VII- Data analysis from Gambiers Archipelago to Papeete (figures 9 & 10)

The data set consists of :

- 2 long meridional transects, where no CTD stations were achieved (fig 9a & 9b)
- the “spezial STEFI EXPERIMENT”, occurring around the Marqueses Archipelago, where a glider and drifting profilers were deployed .

STEFI EXPERIMENT is detailed in figures 10a and 10b. Occurring from July 21 to August 10 , with rather stable weather conditions , the time variability may be considered as low.

The “warm event” (Tmax 27.2°C) recorded on the NW corner of Nuku Hiva might be a SBE38 bias following a 2 days stop at anchor , if not a true physical anomaly caused by a cornering circulation modified by the island ? Cross comparison with surface data from 24 valid CTD profiles (stations 122 to 125, fig 10b) shows a good correlation, *with median differences around 0.0004 °C and 0.0024 PSU*. *It must be again emphasized that TSG and CTD data are true independent variables (no cross calibration)*.

Figure 9a : TSG QC data from Gambiers to Tahiti

Figure 9b : TSG QC data from Gambiers to Tahiti

Figure 10a : TSG QC data for STEFI EXPERIMENT (Marqueses isl.)

Figure 10b : (CTD - TSG) differences for STEFI EXPERIMENT (Marqueses isl.)

VIII- Data analysis from Coral experiment in the Gambiers lagoon (fig 11)

Tara spent 12 days (30/06 > 12/07) working inside the lagoon for a coral sampling session.

7 stations (sta 114-121) were achieved on very shallow grounds (depth < 10m) , among which 6 valid CTD profiles could be used for TSG intercomparison.

6 is a too small figure to allow robust statistics but though it can be seen on fig 11b that :

- SSS differences range in (± 0.004 PSU) centred on ($- 0.001$ PSU), which is excellent.
- SST differences range in ($- 0.04$ °C , $+0.08$ °C) centred on ($+ 0.01$ °C), which is not so good .This may be easily explained by the fact that on 5 to 10m bathymetry, vertical T profiles can show strong surface gradients between TSG pumping level (1.5m) and first available CTD data (2 or 3 m).

date	sta nb	CTD profile number	Comments
	VALID		USHUALA
03/01/2011	84	tara_sbe_9C_110103_01	Bottle 8 failed, UVP analog problem
03/01/2011	84	tara_sbe_9C_110103_02	
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_01	UVP not working
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_02	UVP not working DCM water @90m
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_03	UVP not working DCM water @90m CHECK SAL ! 1 NOK
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_04	UVP not working DCM water @90m CHECK SAL ! 1 NOK
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_05	UVP not working DCM water @90m
06/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110106_06	UVP not working DCM water @90m
07/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110107_01	UVP not working MESO
07/01/2011	85	tara_sbe_9C_110107_02	UVP not working MESO
09/01/2011	86	tara_sbe_9C_110109_01	no bottles , searam badly programmed (.con missing)
09/01/2011	86	tara_sbe_9C_110109_02	bottles/searam OK
17/01/2011	87	tara_sbe_9s_110117_01	On green spectra cable
22/01/2011	88	tara_sbe_9s_110122_01	On green spectra cable
27/01/2011	89	tara_sbe_9s_110127_01	On green spectra cable
			PUERTO WILLIAMS
21/02/2011	90	tara_sbe_9s_110221_01	On green spectra cable. Salinities
25/02/2011	91	tara_sbe_9s_110225_01	On green spectra cable
26/02/2011	92	tara_sbe_9s_110226_01	On green spectra cable
			VALPARAISO
03/11/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110311_01	UVP lights flashing fast on test
03/12/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110312_01	
03/12/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110312_02	4 kn drift!
03/12/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110312_03	4 kn drift!
03/12/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110312_04	4 kn drift!
03/14/2011	93	tara_sbe_9C_110313_01	Marginal. UVP did not reach start depths
03/16/2011	94	tara_sbe_9C_110316_01	CTD #1 transect
03/17/2011	94	tara_sbe_9C_110317_01	CTD #2 transect
03/18/2011	94	tara_sbe_9C_110318_01	Short Stn
03/18/2011	94	tara_sbe_9C_110318_02	Short Stn
03/19/2011	95	tara_sbe_9C_110319_01	CTD #1 transect
03/20/2011	95	tara_sbe_9C_110320_01	CTD #2 transect. Salinities
03/21/2011	95	tara_sbe_9C_110321_01	Short Stn
03/21/2011	95	tara_sbe_9C_110321_02	Short Stn
03/22/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110322_01	CTD #1 transect
03/23/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110323_01	CTD #2 transect
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_01	Short Station
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_02	
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_03	DCM water #1
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_04	DCM water #2
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_05	DCM water #3
03/24/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110324_06	DCM water #4
03/25/2011	96	tara_sbe_9C_110325_01	night CTD
27/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110327_01	
27/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110327_02	
28/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110328_01	Nutricline water #1

28/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110328_02	Nutricline water #2
28/03/2011	97	X	Nutricline water #3 RUN FLASH INITIALISE - only seen after ncast=8
28/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110328_04	Nutricline water #4 2x sections Bad "F" data - will need editing manually
28/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110328_05	DCM water #1
28/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110328_06	DCM water #2
29/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110329_01	DCM water #3
29/03/2011	97	tara_sbe_9C_110329_02	DCM water #4
			EASTER ISLAND
02/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110402_01	CTD #1 transect
03/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110403_01	CTD #2 transect
03/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110403_02	
03/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110403_03	DCM water #1
03/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110403_04	DCM water #2
03/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110403_05	DCM water #3
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_01	DCM water #4
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_02	MESO cast #1
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_03	MESO cast #2
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_04	MESO cast #3
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_05	MESO cast #4
04/04/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110404_06	MESO cast #5, "F"'s in data at end of cast
04/05/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110405_01	Night Cast
04/05/2011	98	tara_sbe_9C_110405_02	DCM water #5
04/09/2011	99	tara_sbe_9C_110409_01	
04/09/2011	99	tara_sbe_9C_110409_02	
04/14/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110414_01	CTD #1 transect
04/15/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110415_01	Night CTD
04/15/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110415_02	Day sampling CTD
04/16/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110416_01	MESO cast #1
04/16/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110416_02	MESO cast #2
04/16/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110416_03	MESO cast #3
04/16/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110416_04	MESO cast #4
04/16/2011	100	tara_sbe_9C_110416_05	MESO cast #5
04/19/2011	101	tara_sbe_9C_110419_01	UVP extract failed. Solved later: NaN in PIDfile, set=1. Salinities
04/21/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110421_01	
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_01	Night cast. UVP starts at 70m
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_02	MESO cast #1
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_03	MESO cast #2
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_04	MESO cast #3
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_05	MESO cast #4
04/22/2011	102	tara_sbe_9C_110422_06	
			GUAYAQUIL
05/02/2011	103	tara_sbe_9C_110502_01	Equatorial Transect CTD #1
05/02/2011	104	tara_sbe_9C_110502_02	Equatorial Transect CTD #2
05/03/2011	105	tara_sbe_9C_110503_01	Equatorial Transect CTD #3
05/03/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110503_02	No UVP.Preparegrab error + CAM error on Light test?
05/03/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110503_03	
05/04/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110504_01	Night Cast
05/04/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110504_02	MESO cast #1
05/04/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110504_03	MESO cast #2
05/04/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110504_04	MESO cast #3
05/04/2011	106	tara_sbe_9C_110504_05	MESO cast #4
			GALAPAGOS
05/11/2011	107	tara_sbe_9C_110511_01	Equatorial Transect CTD #4

05/11/2011	108	tara_sbe_9C_110511_02	Equatorial Transect CTD #5. NO UVP: pwr ext. cable bad connections?
05/12/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110512_01	Equatorial Transect CTD #6
05/12/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110512_02	Long Station, same number as last CTD
05/12/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110512_03	
13/05/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110513_01	Night Cast
13/05/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110513_02	Meso #1 - FLASH ERRORS - Data GOOD until 70m UPCAST
13/05/2011	109	X	Meso #2 - FLASH ERRORS - Data BAD until 376m UPCAST
13/05/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110513_04	Meso #3
13/05/2011	109	tara_sbe_9C_110513_05	Meso #4 - UVP starts 15m on downcast, soak as usual?
			GUAYAQUIL
21/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110521_01	Winch stopped 25 minutes at 245m. 2x ISUS files merged
21/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110521_02	
21/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110521_03	
22/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110522_01	
22/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110522_02	
22/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110522_03	
22/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110522_04	
22/05/2011	110	tara_sbe_9C_110522_05	End of cast by "memory full". 1462m on upcast
29/05/2011	111_01	tara_sbe_9C_110529_01	
30/05/2011	111_02	tara_sbe_9C_110530_01	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_01	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_02	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_03	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_04	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_05	
31/05/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110531_06	
01/06/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110601_01	
01/06/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110601_02	
01/06/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110601_03	
01/06/2011	111	tara_sbe_9C_110601_04	
02/06/2011	111_03	tara_sbe_9C_110602_01	
03/06/2011	111_04	tara_sbe_9C_110603_01	
04/06/2011	111_05	tara_sbe_9C_110604_01	Salinities
05/06/2011	111_06	tara_sbe_9C_110605_01	
06/06/2011	111_07	tara_sbe_9C_110606_01	
07/06/2011	111_08	tara_sbe_9C_110607_01	
08/06/2011	111_09	tara_sbe_9C_110608_01	
14/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110614_01	
14/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110614_02	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_01	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_02	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_03	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_04	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_05	
15/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110615_06	
16/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110616_01	
16/06/2011	112	tara_sbe_9C_110616_02	
17/06/2011	112_01	tara_sbe_9C_110617_01	UVP failed for unknown reason
17/06/2011	112_02	tara_sbe_9C_110617_02	

19/06/2011	113	tara_sbe_9C_110619_01	
26/06/2011	114	tara_sbe_9C_110626_01	Fringing Reef - phantom data starting 17m (manual edited hex)
29/06/2011	115	tara_sbe_9C_110629_01	Fringing Reef
30/06/2011	116	tara_sbe_9C_110630_01	Fringing Reef - NIGHT
01/07/2011	117	tara_sbe_9C_110701_01	Central Lagoon - NIGHT
02/07/2011	118	tara_sbe_9C_110702_01	Central Lagoon - DAY
06/07/2011	119	tara_sbe_9C_110706_01	Inner Reef + Bummies - NIGHT - phantom data (manual edited hex)
06/07/2011	120	tara_sbe_9C_110706_02	Inner Reef + Bummies - DAY
09/07/2011	121	tara_sbe_9C_110709_01	Outer Reef - DAY - bottles did not close, sal bad to 15m
09/07/2011	121	tara_sbe_9C_110709_02	Outer Reef - DAY - repeat cast
			MARQUISES - STEFI EXPERIMENT
20/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110720_01	TEST only
26/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110726_01	STATION "GABY"
26/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110726_02	CTD took a big hit ondeck
27/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110727_01	NIGHT ctd
27/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110727_02	MESO #1
27/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110727_03	MESO #2, star Oddies cal.
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_01	MESO #3
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_02	MESO #4
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_03	DCM #1
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_04	DCM #2
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_05	DCM #3
28/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110728_06	DCM #4
29/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110729_01	Transect to Nuku Hiva: "Daniele 1"
29/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110729_02	Transect to Nuku Hiva: "Daniele 2"
29/07/2011	122	tara_sbe_9C_110729_03	Transect to Nuku Hiva: "Daniele 3"
31/07/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110731_01	UVP did not process DAT,BRU,PID
31/07/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110731_02	STATION "ERIC"
01/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110801_01	
01/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110801_02	Bottom Mixed Layer #1 - Bottles did not close - confile not selected
01/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110801_03	Bottom Mixed Layer #1
01/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110801_04	Bottom Mixed Layer #2
01/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110801_05	Bottom Mixed Layer #3
02/08/2011	123	tara_sbe_9C_110802_01	Bottom Mixed Layer #4
04/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110804_01	DIURNAL CYCLE #1 - STATION "ROMAIN"
04/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110804_02	DIURNAL CYCLE #2 - change of station position
04/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110804_03	Normal Deep Day CTD - STATION "TROUBLE"
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_01	DIURNAL CYCLE #1 + shallow Chief Sci CTD
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_02	DIURNAL CYCLE #2 + NIGHT CTD FLASH ERRORS will need manual editing FOR SURFACE TO 36m
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_03	DIURNAL CYCLE #3 NIGHT
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_04	DIURNAL CYCLE #4 NIGHT
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_05	BML #1
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_06	BML #2
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_07	BML #3
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_08	DIURNAL CYCLE #5 DAY
05/08/2011	124	tara_sbe_9C_110805_09	BML #4
08/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110808_01	STATION "ETIENNE"
08/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110808_02	Salinities
08/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110808_03	
09/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110809_01	BML #1
09/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110809_02	BML #2
09/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110809_03	BML #3
09/08/2011	125	tara_sbe_9C_110809_04	BML #4

Chapter 4

Data processing and analysis from Tahiti to San Diego

I- TSG raw data extraction , calibration and filtering

Start : Papeete (Tahiti) on 26/08/2011 20:39:55

End : San Diego(Cal/ USA) on 26/10/2011 20:42:23

Calibrating T(SBE38) and S(SBE45) through T and C(SBE45) from pre- an post-campaign Seabird calibrations gives the following corrections for the period :

T correction is 10 times smaller than the SBE38 initial accuracy.(0.002°C)

S correction is in average 1.5 times greater than SBE45 initial accuracy. (0.005 PSU)

The raw data were almost clean, very few points were removed by prefiltering . The ACS 25mn noise (not always existent along the file) was removed by the $\pm 6\text{mn}$ window running median filter.

II- CTD profiles assimilation

CTD stations	number	% total
total	72	100%
discarded	16	22%
no 3-4db data	25	35%
valid for TSG_QC	31	43%

Among the 72 available profiles from LOV(see listing at the end) , only 31 were useful for TSG intercalibration;

25 profiles showed no surface data and 16 were discarded due to random and non significant (CTD-TSG) differences (red dots on figure 2). Half of those differences appear for the last profiles (station 135, close to Californian shore) and are discussed later in chapter IV .

Figure 2 : (CTD-TSG) differences and valid/ non valid CTD stations

Screening the whole set of valid CTD data , we decided to apply corrections on TSG only in the area of stations 127, 129 and 130 where a significant salinity offset was obvious on TSG data. The difference distributions on the final QC validated data appear on figure 3 :

Figure 3 : (CTD-TSG) differences distribution on the final QC validated data

Median differences lay in the order of magnitude of the instrumental accuracies and the distribution, although not Gaussian are roughly symmetrical.

III- Data analysis for leg Tahiti to Hawaii

SST and SSS time series and chart plotted appear on figure 4.

An abrupt drop in temperature (-1.6°C) and salinity (- 2.5 PSU) occurs at latitude 10°N while Tara was steaming North at 8 knts .On the zoomed pictures (fig 5), the “cuvette” along track diameter is assessed to ≈ 30 miles.

At that latitude and time period (oct 13), this may be interpreted as the signature of a strong tropical rain event (past or present).

Other such events might well have occurred during this leg between 10S and 10N and may be hidden by the gaps in TSG data on fig 4.

Figure 4 : TSG QC data from Tahiti to Hawaii

Figure 5 : Tropical rain event causing an abrupt T and S at 10°N on the leg from Tahiti to Hawaii

IV- Data analysis from Hawaii to San Diego

Figure 6a : TSG QC data from Hawaii to San Diego

A sharp SSS drop after station 131 (N of Hawaii) is probably the signature of another rain event . Other such rain events might explain the further SSS drops correlated with SST drops, as detailed on the zoom and TS diagram on figure 6b.

While correlation between TSG and CTD data remain rather good during the whole transit in the central Pacific basin (see fig 2), strong anomalies appear during the last station (sta135, longitude 121W) when Tara reaches the continental slope and crosses the North Pacific Current. (zoom on figure 7).

The SST/SSS signature of this cold fresh current is visible on fig 6c starting around station 133 (130W) to the Californian shore.

CTD/TSG anomalies may be explained by a strong stratification in the surface layer. Another possible explanation might be heavy weather conditions during station 135, as SST signal looks rather noisy.

Anyway this is the reason why we have discarded CTD station 135 in the TSG_QC validation process.

Figure 6c : TSG QC data from Hawaii to San Diego

Figure 7 :strong anomalies between TSG and CTD data when sailing through the North PacificCurrent

date	stanumber	Ctd data file name	Comments
			PAPEETE
28/08/2011	126	tara_sbe_9C_110828_00	Short Station. CAST ABORTED (pulley problems) NO UVP, no hdr
28/08/2011	126	tara_sbe_9C_110828_01	NO UVP - no idea why
28/08/2011	126	tara_sbe_9C_110828_02	UVP started @15m
			Long Station
30/08/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110830_01	TRANSECT CTD #1 Bad data at end of file: Ran FLASH INITIALISE.
31/08/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110831_01	NIGHT CTD - starting UVP with I/O shunt "on deck" not press. UVP OK
31/08/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110831_02	UVP OK
31/08/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110831_03	UVP stopped while on deck, Voltage?
01/09/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110901_01	DCM #1, UVP OK
01/09/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110901_02	DCM #2, NO UVP - folder contains garbage and only hdr file
02/09/2011	127	tara_sbe_9C_110902_01	DCM #3. CTD unresponsive after this cast. Eventually OK. UVP started at 56m
			Long Station
03/09/2011	128	tara_sbe_9C_110903_01	TRANSECT CTD #1
04/09/2011	128	tara_sbe_9C_110904_01	TRANSECT CTD #2
04/09/2011	128	tara_sbe_9C_110904_02	NIGHT CTD
04/09/2011	128	tara_sbe_9C_110904_03	DAY CTD. UVP starts at 48m (soak started at > 15m)
04/09/2011	128	tara_sbe_9C_110904_04	Chief ScI sampling
			Long Station
09/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110909_01	TRANSECT CTD #1
10/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110910_01	DAY CTD
10/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110910_02	Chief ScI sampling
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_01	NIGHT CTD
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_02	DCM #1
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_03	DCM #2
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_04	DCM #3
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_05	DCM #4
11/09/2011	129	tara_sbe_9C_110911_06	DCM #5
			Short Station
13/09/2011	130	tara_sbe_9C_110913_01	Star Oddie Cal + salinities
13/09/2011	130	tara_sbe_9C_110913_02	Big Pulley shackle worked loose....
			HONOLULU
29/09/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_110929_01	
30/09/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_110930_01	
30/09/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_110930_02	
30/09/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_110930_03	
30/09/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_110930_04	Partial download to 133m downcast
30/09/2011	131	X	Download cancelled
01/10/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_111001_01	
01/10/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_111001_02	
01/10/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_111001_03	
01/10/2011	131	tara_sbe_9C_111001_04	
04/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111004_01	
04/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111004_02	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_01	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_02	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_03	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_04	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_05	
05/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111005_06	
06/10/2011	132	tara_sbe_9C_111006_01	Flash errors from 580m upcast, no bottle file
06/10/2011	132	X	Flash errors NO data file
08/10/2011	132_02	tara_sbe_9C_111008_01	

11/10/2011	132_03	tara_sbe_9C_111010_01	Salinity
18/10/2011	133_01	tara_sbe_9C_111018_01	
18/10/2011	133_02	tara_sbe_9C_111018_02	
18/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111018_03	
18/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111018_04	
19/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111019_01	
19/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111019_02	
19/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111019_03	
19/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111019_04	
20/10/2011	133	tara_sbe_9C_111020_01	
21/10/2011	133_03	tara_sbe_9C_111021_01	
21/10/2011	133_04	tara_sbe_9C_111021_02	
22/10/2011	134	tara_sbe_9C_111022_01	
22/10/2011	134	tara_sbe_9C_111022_02	
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111023_01	
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111023_02	
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111024_01	
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111024_02	CANNOT FIND FILE
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111024_03	Bottle #1 FAILED
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111024_04	
23/11/2011	135	tara_sbe_9C_111024_05	Bottle #1 FAILED
25/10/2011	135_01	tara_sbe_9C_111025_01	Bottle #1 FAILED
25/10/2011	135_01	tara_sbe_9C_111025_02	Bottle #1 FAILED
25/10/2011	135_01	tara_sbe_9C_111025_03	Bottle #1 FAILED
			SAN DIEGO

Chapter 5

Data processing and analysis from San Diego to Savannah through Panama Canal

I- TSG raw data extraction , calibration and filtering

Start : San Diego (USA) on 24/11/2011 16:41:51

End : Savannah (USA) on 20/01/2012 02:33:00

Calibrating T(SBE38) and S(SBE45) through T and C(SBE45) from pre- an post-campaign Seabird calibrations gives the following corrections for the period :

T correction is 10 times smaller than the SBE38 initial accuracy.(0.002°C)

S correction is in average 1.5 time greater than the SBE45 initial accuracy. (0.005 PSU)

The raw data were more noisy than for the previous pacific legs , outliers were removed by prefiltering .The ACS 25mn noise was removed by the ± 6 mn window running median filter.

II- CTD profiles assimilation

CTD stations	number	% total
total	66	100%
discarded	11	17%
no 3-4db data	4	6%
valid for TSG_QC	51	77%

Among the 66 available profiles from LOV(see listing at the end) , 51were useful for TSG intercalibration; 4 profiles showed no surface data .

11 profiles were discarded due to random and non significant (CTD-TSG) differences (red dots on figure 2)

Screening the whole set of valid CTD data , *we decided to apply corrections on TSG* around the stations or group of stations where the difference distributions showed asymetrical behaviour and/or significant median differences . Those corrections applied for stations 136, 137, 138+139, 142+143 within the following ranges :

$-0.008 < \text{corr SSS} < + 0.003 \text{ PSU}$

$-0.008 < \text{corr SST} < + 0.024 \text{ °C}$

The difference distributions on the whole set of QC validated data appear on figure 3

Median differences are 10 time smaller than the instrumental accuracies .

Figure 2 : (CTD-TSG) differences and valid/ non valid CTD stations

Figure 3 : (CTD-TSG) differences distribution on the final QC validated data

III- Data analysis from San Diego to Savannah through Panama

Figure 4a and 4b show SSS and SST data for the whole period . As expected pacific waters are fresher than Carribean waters .

At the end of the Pacific leg, when Tara enters the Gulf of Panama , a strong SSS anomaly appears (drop from 33 to 26 PSU) . CTD profiles on station 140 do confirm those SSS values .(zoom in figure 5). Most of the vertical salinity gradient occurs in the surface layer (0- 40m).

This is the known signature of the rain season (av 4000mm/year) and river outflows in the Panama Gulf, phenomena already well documented by satellites (SMOS) and TSG data from commercial ships crossing the Canal.

Detailed data for the Caribbean leg to Savannah appear on figure 6.

Figure 4a : TSG QC data from San Diego to Savannah

Figure 4b : TSG QC data from San Diego to Savannah

Figure 5 : SSS anomaly and station 140 CTD profile when entering Gulf of Panama

Figure 6 : TSG QC data from Panama to Savannah

Chapter 6

Data processing and analysis from Savannah to Lorient

I- TSG raw data extraction , calibration and filtering

Start: Savannah (USA) on 26/01/2012 20:27:25

End : Lorient (Fr) on 29/03/2012 23:59:00

Calibrating T(SBE38) and S(SBE45) through T and C(SBE45) from pre- an post-campaign Seabird calibrations gives the following corrections for the period :

T correction is 10 times smaller than the SBE38 initial accuracy.(0.002°C)

S correction is in average 2.5 times greater than the SBE45 initial accuracy. (0.005 PSU)

The raw data were slightly noisy on some occurrences , only few outliers were hence removed by prefiltering .The ACS 25mn noise was removed by the ± 6 mn window running median filter.

II- CTD profiles assimilation

CTD stations	number	% total
total	82	100%
discarded	2	2%
no 3-4db data	23	28%
valid for TSG_QC	57	70%

Among the 82 available profiles from LOV(see listing at the end) , 57 were useful for TSG intercalibration; 23 profiles showed no surface data .

2 profiles were discarded due to random and non significant (CTD-TSG) differences .

Screening the whole set of valid CTD data, median differences look significant, (especially on SSS , figure 2b) and show trends (figure 2a) along the whole N Atlantic leg (4th degree polynomial fit). Therefore we decided to apply corrections to TSG data , for each individual leg in order to detrend the whole serie , as follow :

Leg	correction on SST (°C)	correction on SSS (PSU)
Savannah -New York	0.0281	- 0.0144
New York Bermuda	- 0.0018	- 0.001
Bermuda Azores	- 0.0037	- 0.0094
Azores Lorient	- 0.005	- 0.0185

The difference distributions on the final of QC validated data after those corrections appear on figure 2c : they look almost Gaussian.

Figure 2a : (CTD-TSG) differences with trends and valid/ non valid CTD stations

Figure 2b : (CTD-TSG) differences distribution before intercalibration

Figure 2c : (CTD-TSG) differences distribution on the final QC data after intercalibration

III- Data analysis from Savannah to Lorient

Figure 3a and 3b show SSS and SST data for the whole Atlantic leg. The Gulf Stream signature is well seen when sailing from Savannah to Bermuda (figure 4). The various profiles of station 146 added with the TSG data between NY and Bermuda should produce a nice orthogonal section

Figure 3a : TSG QC time series from Savannah to Lorient

Figure 3b : TSG QC data from Savannah to Lorient

Figure 4 : TSG QC data from Savannah to Bermuda, crossing the Gulf Stream

Chapter 7

TECHNICAL APPENDIX

Seabird calibration reports and hardware configurations for TSG

Final report on CTD profiles validation

I- Hardware configuration

Sea water circuits for all underway instruments in dry lab :
TSG downstream with ACS, Vortex debubbler and 0.2µ filter (5mn /30mn)

The data acquisition chain and its various configurations are detailed here:

TSG configuration : problems and evolutions

date	NMEA configuration	PC acquisition	comments
sept-dec 09	Ship's Nmea through interface box	Seasave	NMEA stream unreliable many randoms crashes
dec09- jul10	own GPS through interface box	Seasave	interface box unreliable still random crashes
sept10-march12	own GPS on PC's USB port	Matlab	all OK
jun11-march 12	Fluorometer added on USB port	Matlab	all OK

II- TSG raw data calibration

T1 and C sensors on SBE45 and T2 sensor on SBE38 have been factory calibrated :

- On purchase (07/05/2009) before departure
- During stopover at Capetown (04/08/2010)
- After arrival at Lorient (13/06/2012)

Calibration sheets returned by Seabird are copied in the next pages. Postslope on C and Temperature offsets are summarized in the following table :

Sensors	Correction	07/05/2009	04/08/2010	04/08/2010	13/06/2012
SBE45 -T1	offset(millideg)	0.72	0	-0.12	0
SBE45 -C	slope C	0.9993577	1.00000	1.0004614	1.00000
SBE38-T2	offset(millideg)	0.09	0	0.14	0

We assume that sensors are drifting linearly between calibrations and we apply the calibration process recommended by Seabird in its “application note n°31” (whose relevant parts are given next):

- By linear interpolation between calibration dates, we compute C islope and offsets on T45 and T38 for the julian date of each data.
- We apply the T offset to each T45 and T38 data to compute T45cal and SSTcal
- We apply the islope to C to compute Ccal
- Using Unesco equation (with ITS90 to ITS68 conversion on T45cal) , we compute a calibrated salinity SSScal (T45cal,Ccal)

Corresponding code for Capetown to Lorient (year 2 & 3):

```
time1=datenum('08/04/2010') % precruise calibration date
time2=datenum('06/01/2012') % postcruise calibration date
dtime=time2-time1 % elapsed time btw pre and post calibrations

ps=1.0004614 % postcruise slope on C for SBE45
DT38= 0.00014 % postcruise delta T for SBE38
DT45= -0.00012 % postcruise delta T for SBE45

% compute linear regression on C slope: slope(x)= 1- alpha*x
% x is number of elapsed days since precalibration
alpha= (1-1/ps)/dtime % the Seabird note formula

% compute linear regression on T offset : R(x)= beta*x .
beta38=DT38/dtime
beta45=DT45/dtime

% Ccal= C45 * slope(x)
% T45cal= T45- R45(x)
% SSTcal= T38- R38(x)
% SSScal=sw_salt (Ctrue*10/sw_c3515 ,1.00024*T45cal ,1.5) UNESCO equation
```

Corresponding code for Lorient to Capetown (year 1: calibration correction on S , not on C) :

```
time1=datenum('05/13/2009') % precruise calibration date
time2=datenum('08/04/2010') % postcruise calibration date
dtime=time2-time1

ps= 0.9993577 %postcruise slope on C for SBE45
DT38= 0.00009 % postcruise delta T for SBE38

% compute linear regression on C slope: slope(x)= 1- alpha*x
% x is number of elapsed days since precalibration
alpha= (1-1/ps)/dtime

% compute linear regression on T offset : R38(x)= beta38*x
Beta38=DT38/dtime

% SSTcal= T38- R38(x)
% SSScal= S45*slope(x) C slope correction applied on raw salinity S45 computed from (T45,C)
```

Computing Temperature and Conductivity *Slope* and *Offset* Correction Coefficients from Laboratory Calibrations and Salinity Bottle Samples

Conductivity Sensors

The conductivity sensor *slope* and *offset* entries in the configuration (.con or .xmlcon) file in SEASOFT permit the user to make corrections for sensor drift between calibrations. The correction formula is:

$$(\text{corrected conductivity}) = \text{slope} * (\text{computed conductivity}) + \text{offset}$$

where :

$$\text{slope} = (\text{true conductivity span}) / (\text{instrument reading conductivity span})$$

$$\text{offset} = (\text{true conductivity} - \text{instrument reading conductivity}) * \text{slope} \quad \text{measured at } 0 \text{ S/m}$$

For newly calibrated sensors, use slope = 1.0, offset = 0.0.

Sea-Bird conductivity sensors usually drift by changing span (the slope of the calibration curve), and changes are typically toward lower conductivity readings with time. Any offset error in conductivity (error at 0 S/m) is usually due to electronics drift, typically less than ± 0.0001 S/m per year. Offsets greater than ± 0.0002 S/m per year are symptomatic of sensor malfunction. **Therefore, Sea-Bird recommends that conductivity drift corrections be made by assuming no offset error, unless there is strong evidence to the contrary or a special need.**

Correcting for Conductivity Drift Based on Pre- and Post-Cruise Laboratory Calibrations

Suppose a conductivity sensor is calibrated (pre-cruise), then immediately used at sea, and then returned for post-cruise calibration. The pre- and post-cruise calibration data can be used to generate a slope correction for data obtained between the pre- and post-cruise calibrations.

If α is the conductivity computed from the pre-cruise bath data (temperature and frequency) using post-cruise calibration coefficients and β is the true conductivity in the pre-cruise bath, then:

$$\text{postslope} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i)(\beta_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i)(\alpha_i)} \quad (\text{postslope is typically } < 1.0)$$

Sea-Bird calculates and prints the value for postslope on the conductivity calibration sheet for all calibrations since February 1995 (see *Appendix I: Example Conductivity Calibration Sheet*)

To correct conductivity data taken between pre- and post-cruise calibrations:

$$\text{islope} = 1.0 + (b / n) [(1 / \text{postslope}) - 1.0]$$

where

islope = interpolated slope; this is the value to enter in the configuration (.con or .xmlcon) file

b = number of days between pre-cruise calibration and the cast to be corrected

n = number of days between pre- and post-cruise calibrations

postslope = slope from calibration sheet as calculated above (see *Appendix I: Example Conductivity Calibration Sheet*)

In the configuration (.con or .xmlcon) file, use the pre-cruise calibration coefficients and use islope for the value of slope.*

Note: In our SEASOFT V2 suite of programs, edit the CTD configuration (.con or .xmlcon) file using the Configure Inputs menu in Seasave V7 (real-time data acquisition software) or the Configure menu in SBE Data Processing (data processing software).

For typical conductivity drift rates (equivalent to -0.003 PSU/month), islope does not need to be recalculated more frequently than at weekly intervals.

Temperature Sensors

The temperature sensor *slope* and *offset* entries in the configuration (.con or .xmlcon) file in SEASOFT permit the user to make corrections for sensor drift between calibrations. The correction formula is:

$$\text{corrected temperature} = \text{slope} * (\text{computed temperature}) + \text{offset}$$

where :

$$\text{slope} = (\text{true temperature span}) / (\text{instrument reading temperature span})$$

$$\text{offset} = (\text{true temperature} - \text{instrument reading temperature}) * \text{slope} \quad \text{measured at } 0.0 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

For newly calibrated sensors, use slope = 1.0, offset = 0.0.

Sea-Bird temperature sensors usually drift by changing offset (an error of equal magnitude at all temperatures). In general, the drift can be toward higher or lower temperature with time; however, for a specific sensor the drift remains the same sign (direction) for many consecutive years. Many years of experience with thousands of sensors indicates that the drift is smooth and uniform with time, allowing users to make very accurate drift corrections to field data based only on pre- and post-cruise laboratory calibrations.

Span errors cause slope errors, as described in the equation for slope above. Sea-Bird temperature sensors rarely exhibit span errors larger than 0.005 °C over the range -5 to 35 °C, even after years of drift. Temperature calibrations performed at Sea-Bird since January 1995 have slope errors less than 0.0002 °C in 30 °C. Prior to January 1995, some calibrations were delivered that include slope errors up to 0.004 °C in 30 °C because of undetected systematic errors in calibration. A slope error that increases by more than ±0.0002 [°C per °C per year] indicates an unusual aging of electronic components and is symptomatic of sensor malfunction. **Therefore, Sea-Bird recommends that drift corrections**

to temperature sensors be made assuming no slope error, unless there is strong evidence to the contrary or a special need.

Calibration checks at-sea are advisable for consistency checks of the sensor drift rate and for early detection of sensor malfunction. However, data from reversing thermometers is rarely accurate enough to make calibration corrections that are better than those possible by shore-based laboratory calibrations. **For the SBE 9plus**, a proven alternate consistency check is to use dual SBE 3 temperature sensors on the CTD and to track the difference in drift rates between the two sensors. In the deep ocean, where temperatures are uniform, the difference in temperature measured by two sensors can be resolved to better than 0.0002 °C and will change smoothly with time as predicted by the difference in drift rates of the two sensors.

Correcting for Temperature Drift Based on Pre- and Post-Cruise Laboratory Calibrations

Suppose a temperature sensor is calibrated (pre-cruise), then immediately used at-sea, and then returned for post-cruise calibration. The pre- and post-cruise calibration data can be used to generate an offset correction for data obtained between the pre- and post-cruise calibrations.

Calibration coefficients are calculated with the post-cruise calibration. Using the pre-cruise bath data and the post-cruise calibration coefficients, a mean residual over the calibration temperature range is calculated.

$$\text{residual} = \text{instrument temperature} - \text{bath temperature}$$

Sea-Bird calculates and prints the value for the residual on the temperature calibration sheet (see *Appendix II: Example Temperature Calibration Sheet*).

To correct temperature data taken between pre- and post-cruise calibrations:

$$\text{Offset} = b * (\text{residual} / n)$$

where

b = number of days between pre-cruise calibration and the cast to be corrected

n = number of days between pre- and post-cruise calibrations

residual = residual from calibration sheet as described above (see *Appendix II: Example Temperature Calibration Sheet*)

Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.
 13431 NE 20th Street, Bellevue, WA 98005-2010 USA
 Phone: (+1) 425-643-9866 Fax (+1) 425-643-9954 Email: seabird@seabird.com

SENSOR SERIAL NUMBER: 0497
 CALIBRATION DATE: 11-May-12

SBE 38 TEMPERATURE CALIBRATION DATA
 ITS-90 TEMPERATURE SCALE

ITS-90 COEFFICIENTS
 a0 = 5.616064e-005
 a1 = 2.675443e-004
 a2 = -1.988252e-005
 a3 = 1.383090e-007

BATH TEMP (ITS-90)	INSTRUMENT OUTPUT	INST TEMP (ITS-90)	RESIDUAL (ITS-90)
-1.50000	823759.3	-1.49996	0.00004
1.00000	733701.3	1.00000	-0.00000
4.50010	625762.8	4.49998	-0.00012
8.00000	535499.2	7.99998	-0.00002
11.50010	459747.3	11.50025	0.00015
15.00000	395972.3	15.00000	0.00000
18.50000	342091.0	18.49999	-0.00001
22.00000	296425.2	21.99997	-0.00003
25.50000	257604.3	25.49991	-0.00009
29.00010	224496.7	29.00017	0.00007
32.50000	196184.8	32.50000	0.00000

Temperature ITS-90 = $1/(a0 + a1[ln(n)] + a2[ln^2(n)] + a3[ln^3(n)]) - 273.15$ (°C)

Residual = instrument temperature - bath temperature

SBE SEA-BIRD ELECTRONICS, INC.
 13431 NE 20th St, Bellevue, Washington 98005 USA
 Phone: (425) 643-9866 Fax: (425) 643-9954 www.seabird.com

Temperature Calibration Report

Customer:	CNRS/LOV		
Job Number:	67902	Date of Report:	5/11/2012
Model Number:	SBE 38	Serial Number:	380497

Temperature sensors are normally calibrated 'as received', without adjustments, allowing a determination sensor drift. If the calibration identifies a problem, then a second calibration is performed after work is completed. The 'as received' calibration is not performed if the sensor is damaged or non-functional, or by customer request.

An 'as received' calibration certificate is provided, listing coefficients to convert sensor frequency to temperature. Users must choose whether the 'as received' calibration or the previous calibration better represents the sensor condition during deployment. In SEASOFT enter the chosen coefficients. The coefficient 'offset' allows a small correction for drift between calibrations (consult the SEASOFT manual). Calibration coefficients obtained after a repair apply only to subsequent data.

'AS RECEIVED CALIBRATION' Performed Not Performed
 Date: 5/11/2012 Drift since last cal: -0.00008 Degrees Celsius/year
 Comments:

'CALIBRATION AFTER REPAIR' Performed Not Performed
 Date: Drift since Last cal: Degrees Celsius/year
 Comments:

II-2 SBE45 Temperature sensor calibrations

SEA-BIRD ELECTRONICS, INC.
 13431 NE 20th Street, Bellevue, Washington, 98005-2010 USA
 Phone: (425) 643-9866 Fax: (425) 643-9954 Email: seabird@seabird.com

SENSOR SERIAL NUMBER: 0286
 CALIBRATION DATE: 04-Aug-10

SBE 45 TEMPERATURE CALIBRATION DATA
 ITS-90 TEMPERATURE SCALE

ITS-90 COEFFICIENTS

a0 = 1.156137e-004
 a1 = 2.615966e-004
 a2 = -1.409891e-005
 a3 = 1.256734e-007

BATH TEMP (ITS-90)	INSTRUMENT OUTPUT	INST TEMP (ITS-90)	RESIDUAL (ITS-90)
1.0000	510.237.4	1.0000	-0.0000
4.4999	521.296.7	4.4999	0.0000
15.0000	330.617.7	15.0000	-0.0000
18.5000	285.838.2	18.5000	-0.0000
24.0000	228.765.2	24.0000	0.0000
29.0000	187.977.6	29.0000	0.0000
32.5000	164.380.8	32.5000	-0.0000

Temperature ITS-90 = 1/[a0 + a1|ln(a)| + a2[ln(a)]² + a3[ln(a)]³] - 273.15 (°C)

Residual = instrument temperature - bath temperature

Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.
 13431 NE 20th Street, Bellevue, WA 98005-2010 USA
 Phone: (+1) 425-843-9866 Fax (+1) 425-843-9954 Email: seabird@seabird.com

SENSOR SERIAL NUMBER: 0286
 CALIBRATION DATE: 13-Jun-12

SBE 45 TEMPERATURE CALIBRATION DATA
 ITS-90 TEMPERATURE SCALE

ITS-90 COEFFICIENTS
 a0 = 5.161235e-005
 a1 = 2.767857e-004
 a2 = -2.612239e-006
 a3 = 1.574197e-007

BATH TEMP (ITS-90)	INSTRUMENT OUTPUT	INST TEMP (ITS-90)	RESIDUAL (ITS-90)
0.9999	610699.1	0.9999	-0.0000
4.4999	521275.4	4.4999	0.0000
14.9999	330615.1	15.0000	0.0001
18.5000	285838.3	18.4999	-0.0001
23.9999	228768.2	24.0000	0.0001
29.0000	187982.2	29.0000	-0.0000
32.5000	164387.7	32.5000	-0.0000

Temperature ITS-90 = 1/(a0 + a1[ln(n)] + a2[ln²(n)] + a3[ln³(n)]) - 273.15 (°C)
 Residual = instrument temperature - bath temperature

SBE SEA-BIRD ELECTRONICS, INC.
 13431 NE 20th St. Bellevue, Washington 98005 USA
 Phone: (425) 843-9866 Fax: (425) 843-9954 www.seabird.com

Temperature Calibration Report

Customer:	CNRS/LOV	Date of Report:	6/13/2012
Job Number:	67902	Serial Number:	4554627-0286
Model Number:	SBE 45		

Temperature sensors are normally calibrated 'as received', without adjustments, allowing a determination sensor drift. If the calibration identifies a problem, then a second calibration is performed after work is completed. The 'as received' calibration is not performed if the sensor is damaged or non-functional, or by customer request.

An 'as received' calibration certificate is provided, using coefficients to convert sensor frequency to temperature. Users must choose whether the 'as received' calibration or the previous calibration better represents the sensor condition during deployment. In SEASOFT enter the chosen coefficients. The coefficient 'offset' allows a small correction for drift between calibrations (consult the SEASOFT manual). Calibration coefficients obtained after a repair apply only to subsequent data.

'AS RECEIVED CALIBRATION' Performed Not Performed
 Date: 5/25/2012 Drift since last cal: +0.00003 Degrees Celsius/year
 Comments:

'FINAL CALIBRATION' Performed Not Performed
 Date: 6/13/2012 Drift since 04 Aug 10: +0.00006 Degrees Celsius/year
 Comments:

II-3 SBE45 Conductivity sensor calibrations

SEA-BIRD ELECTRONICS, INC.
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SENSOR SERIAL NUMBER: 0286
 CALIBRATION DATE: 04-Aug-10

SBE45 CONDUCTIVITY CALIBRATION DATA
 PSS 1978: C(35,15,0) = 4.2934 Siemens/meter

COEFFICIENTS:

g = -1.014235e+000
 h = -1.592542e-001
 i = -1.737253e-004
 j = -4.064979e-005

CPcor = -9.5700e-006
 CTcor = 3.2500e-006
 WBOTC = 2.6402e-007

BATH TEMP (ITS-90)	BATH SAL (PSU)	BATH COND (Siemens/m)	INST FREQ (Hz)	INST COND (Siemens/m)	RESIDUAL (Siemens/m)
22.0000	0.0000	0.00000	2525.04	0.00000	0.00000
1.0000	34.6392	2.96381	4995.62	2.96380	-0.00001
4.4999	34.6398	3.26970	5183.44	3.26971	0.00001
15.0000	34.5973	4.24758	5742.00	4.24758	0.00000
18.5000	34.5879	4.59133	5925.59	4.59132	-0.00000
24.0000	34.5769	5.14694	6210.59	5.14693	-0.00001
29.0000	34.5699	5.66649	6465.44	5.66650	0.00001
32.5000	34.5652	6.03714	6641.09	6.03713	-0.00001

$$f = \text{INST FREQ} * \text{sqn}(1.0 + \text{WBOTC} * t) / 1000.0$$

$$\text{Conductivity} = (g + hf^2 + if^3 + jf^4) / (1 + \delta t + \epsilon p) \text{ Siemens/meter}$$

t = temperature[°C]; p = pressure[decibars]; δ = CTcor; ϵ = CPcor;

Residual = instrument conductivity - bath conductivity

Date, Slope Correction

SENSOR SERIAL NUMBER: 0386
 CALIBRATION DATE: 25-May-12

SBE 45 CONDUCTIVITY CALIBRATION DATA
 PSS 1978: C(35,15,0) = 4.2934 Siemens/meter

COEFFICIENTS:

a = -1.014799e+000 CPcor = -9.5700e-008
 b = 1.597253e-001 CTcor = 3.2500e-006
 c = -3.558212e-004 WBOTC = 2.6402e-007
 d = 3.650742e-005

BATH TEMP (ITS-90)	BATH SAL (PSU)	BATH COND (Siemens/m)	INST FREQ (Hz)	INST COND (Siemens/m)	RESIDUAL (Siemens/m)
22.0000	0.0000	0.00000	2524.84	0.00000	0.00000
1.0000	34.9219	2.98413	5009.35	2.98412	-0.00001
4.5000	34.9017	3.29199	5197.94	3.29198	-0.00000
15.0000	34.8589	4.27629	5758.80	4.27631	0.00002
18.5000	34.8495	4.62230	5943.09	4.62230	-0.00000
24.0000	34.8387	5.18159	6229.12	5.18157	-0.00002
28.9999	34.8307	5.70440	6484.76	5.70439	-0.00001
32.5000	34.8227	6.07698	6660.74	6.07699	0.00001

f = INST FREQ * sqrt(1.0 + WBOTC * t) / 1000.0
 Conductivity = (g + hf² + i³ + j⁴) / (1 + k + lp) Siemens/meter
 t = temperature[°C]; p = pressure(decibars); k = CTcor; e = CPcor;
 Residual = instrument conductivity - bath conductivity

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Conductivity Calibration Report

Customer:	CNRS/LOV		
Job Number:	67902	Date of Report:	6/13/2012
Model Number	SBE 45	Serial Number:	4554627-0286

Conductivity sensors are normally calibrated 'as received', without cleaning or adjustments, allowing a determination of sensor drift. If the calibration identifies a problem or indicates cell cleaning is necessary, then a second calibration is performed after work is completed. The 'as received' calibration is not performed if the sensor is damaged or non-functional or by customer request.

An 'as received' calibration certificate is provided, listing the coefficients used to convert sensor frequency to conductivity. Users must choose whether the 'as received' calibration or the previous calibration better represents the sensor conditions during deployment. In SEASOFT enter the chosen coefficients. The coefficient 'slope' allows small corrections for drift between calibrations (consult the SEASOFT manual). Calibration coefficients obtained after a repair or cleaning apply only to subsequent data.

'AS RECEIVED CALIBRATION' Performed Not Performed
 Date: 5/25/2012 Drift since last cal: -0.00060 PSU/month*
 Comments:

'CALIBRATION AFTER REPAIR' Performed Not Performed
 Date: 6/13/2012 Drift since Last cal: N/A PSU/month*
 Comments:
 The conductivity cell was replaced.

*Measured at 3.0 S/m
 Cell cleaning and electrode replating tend to reset the conductivity sensor to its original condition. Lack of drift in post-cleaning calibration indicates geometric stability of the cell and electrical stability of the sensor circuit.

Post-processing hydrological data acquired during the expedition TARA OCEANS

Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche

Vincent Taillandier, June 19th 2012

Deliverables

1- LogSheet of the 643 profiles collected and the 9 sensors involved during the expedition. For each profile, quality control and choice of TC pair are provided, in order to be implemented in the standard data processing set up by Marc Picheral.

2- a set of SBE format configuration files (.con file) with respect to each raw data file (.hex file) used in the latter QC data base. Their use imply straightforward modification of processing batch script replacing the a priori name of con file by "%1".

Rationale

The expedition TARA OCEANS aims at qualifying and quantifying marine biodiversity, from bacteria to fishes, of the worldwide pelagic ecosystems. The scientific platform, a two-mast sailing ship of 36m, appears atypical to lead such demanding oceanographic studies. In effect, (i) the Carousel and the nets are less easily conditioned and deployed than in classical platforms; (ii) the synopticity of sampling strategies is more hardly reached in absence of real-time acquisition and fast positioning of the ship; (iii) the analytical protocols are to be lead on reduced wetlab capacities. On the other hand, the long term availability of the platform, the flexibility of station locations during each leg, and the limited cost of exploitation make such expedition well fitted to lead long range and sustainable sampling strategies. This expedition showed its capability to provide multidisciplinary high quality data in coarse but targeted stations that shape the biogeography of our world oceans.

The CTD deployed during the expedition is a Sea Bird Electronics (SBE) 9plus technology. It is composed of two independent water ducts crossing pairs of temperature-conductivity sensors entrained by their own pumps. The first parameter is measured by a thermal cell using SBE3 technology, the second parameter is measured by a resistive cell using SBE4 technology. The sensors were new brand at the beginning of the expedition, they have been factory calibrated once or twice during the expedition period. The pressure is measured by a sole sensor inserted in the SBE9 body.

The CTD is used in combination with the SBE17plus module for autonomous in-situ recording, in absence of electrical cable and slip ring equipped winch. This module supplies power to the CTD, decodes the serial data stream at the resolution of the CTD, and stores the resulting data in a non-volatile memory for later retrieval. The module also operates the Carousel water sampler that fires the 10 Niskin bottles on upcast profiles following a pre-programmed sequence (governed by the pressure sensor). This sequence is armed when a prescribed threshold depth (or a given duration at stationary depth) is reached. In absence of real-time operation, the Carousel dives then surfaces continuously at a fixed speed ranging from 0.5 m/s to 1 m/s. A soak over 20 m is also prescribed at the beginning of each deployment. Individual soak processing has been inserted in Marc's protocol.

Uncertainties of measurement

Regarding this experimental protocol, two main sources of errors can be identified:

First, measurements are acquired at 24 Hz which allow an accurate data processing for metric resolution of vertical profiles. High standards of accuracy can be obtained only if a correct alignment of the CTD data stream is achieved. Please refer the intermediate report (Year 1 Post-Processing by same author) for assessment of such uncertainty of measurement.

Second, long term deployments of the CTD between sensor calibrations (over sometimes more than one year), reinforced by precarious storage and conditioning of the sensors, are welling to significant sensor drifts. However, measurements can be corrected a posteriori using calibration results between pre-cruise and post-cruise baths. Such uncertainties are particularly addressed in the present report considering measured drifts between TC pairs and factory calibrated drifts of individual sensors.

As the most critical sensor is the resistive cell that is inherently exposed to rust, salinity samples can be obtained using some water sampler bottles during CTD profiles, and the difference between CTD salinity and bottle salinity can be used to determine the drift in conductivity with a relatively high accuracy. However in the present case, this protocol significantly heavies logistics of the expedition because salinity samples need to be analyzed at land with an AUTOSAL, taken in discrete depths representative of homogeneous water masses (no real-time acquisition), using double-tap clean bottles associated to sensitive conditioning (under 40°C). That is why salinity samples have not been considered in this post processing task.

Finally, note that the scientific interest is focused on the upper and intermediate oceanic layers in which pelagic ecosystems develop. Their physical properties are more fluctuant (diurnal to seasonal scale variations) than the deep water masses ones (mainly climatic variations). So the high accuracy and stability of measurements is of lower requirement for the topical studies covered by the expedition. We'll consider accuracies in the range of millideg for temperature and centiPSU for salinity in absence of deep water sampling.

Sensor drift corrections

A relative assessment of data quality can be performed after deployments thanks to the acquisition of two independent TC profiles. In that way significant dysfunctions can be avoided, punctually if material obstructs one of the two ducts, or at longer range if a sensor is seriously drifting. These events have been documented on the LogSheet.

Also, quality control exploits the differences obtained between two factory calibrations supposing linear drifts of the sensors during this period. In practice, static drift corrections are performed through [slope] and [offset] values specified in a post-processing instrumental configuration file of each profile (see LogSheet). They have been generated together with the processing batch executable. These coefficients are computed with respect to the following formula:

$$[\text{slope}] = 1 + (t-t_i)/(t_n - t_i) \cdot (1/[\text{postslope}] - 1)$$

$$[\text{offset}] = (t-t_i)/(t_n-t_i) \cdot [\text{residual}]$$

where t_i is the date of pre-cruise bath, t_n the date of post-cruise bath, and t the time of the CTD cast. [postslope] is slope from calibration sheet of the C sensors; [residual] is taken from calibration sheet of the T sensors.

The linear drifts obtained from factory calibrations are compared with the measured misfits between pairs (before drift corrections) for every cast under 500m. They are reported in the following figures:

In upper panels, drifts consigned from factory calibrations are reported for each sensor, continuous lines represent the period of use. In lower panels, in-situ misfits before drift corrections are provided. The comparison of relative drifts (colored areas in upper panels with red lines in lower panels) leads to the following comments:

- temperature relative drifts are consistent for the four periods of sensor turnover. For the first round (oct 2009-Jul2010), linear drifts may not apply but the drifts may be more abrupt with a shift in February 2010. Same for the second round in February 2011. Drifts in the last round appear underestimated.
- salinity relative drift are also consistent for the two first rounds. As soon as conductivity sensors drift in the same way, misfits remain small. On the other hand, comparison is not anymore consistent for the two last rounds, when using sensor SN3677: results suggest that this sensor, which has not been used during the second round, has only drifted after Jul2010.

Relative drifts are now assessed after drift corrections in the following figures. The number of casts positioned in pre-cal and post-cal relative drifts is reported.

Considering left panel, temperature relative drifts are lowered to 0.001 degC after correction. On the other hand considering right panel, a patch of non improvement appears in the upper left part of the figure. It corresponds to the round 4 when SN3677 has been deployed.

Conclusions

An analysis of relative drifts measured in-situ together with factory calibration drifts reveal that the real drifts of sensors is not necessary linear, but somehow abrupt depending on some events.

Such behaviors have been significantly well constrained thanks to efficient turnover for all the sensors, except the conductivity cell SN3677. The collected measurement for this sensor might be more uncertain than from others.

Overall, a nominal accuracy under 0.001 degC and 0.005 PSU has been achieved.

The present qualification is limited to the analysis of samples collected in the band [500m, 1000m], which is not really effective in terms of reproducibility as soon as water properties are not seasonally stable in several oceanic basins crossed by the expedition.